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CHALLENGES IN PSYCHOLOGICAL PREPARATION OF FREESTYLE WRESTLERS DURING THE STAGE OF IMPROVING SPORT SKILLS

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Abstract: The psychological preparation of freestyle wrestlers is critical for optimizing performance outcomes. This synthesis of literature highlights the imperative to integrate self-psychological-preparation-based approaches into psychological preparation strategies. Key strategies including temperament self-assessment, personalized goal-setting, self-regulation methods, cognitive-behavioral techniques, and stress management protocols are essential. The findings emphasize a paradigm shift towards individualized interventions, departing from traditional generic methodologies. Psychological challenges during pre-competition preparation stages, such as uncertainty, pressure, and emotional tolls, necessitate effective strategies. Understanding the sporting character and addressing challenges like self-confidence, fear of failure, and motivational issues are paramount. Bridging the gap in psychological self-preparation requires comprehensive support systems, including structured programs tailored to wrestlers' independence, individualized plans, and integration into training regimens.

Keywords: freestyle wrestling, psychological self-preparation, guidance, resources, skill improvement, individual characteristics, performance optimization, competitions.

Introduction

Freestyle wrestling demands not only physical prowess but also mental resilience, requiring athletes to navigate a plethora of psychological challenges before stepping onto the mat. As the pre-competition preparation stage comprises three distinct periods, each presenting unique psychological hurdles. However, current approaches often overlook the importance of tailored psychological interventions, leaving athletes to grapple with these challenges independently. This article synthesizes literature advocating for a paradigm shift towards integrating self-psychological preparation-based approaches into psychological preparation strategies for freestyle wrestlers. By recognizing athletes' individual preparation abilities, coaches and sports psychologists can tailor interventions to enhance performance outcomes, marking a significant departure from traditional, generic methodologies. This introduction lays the groundwork for exploring key strategies aimed at optimizing psychological readi-

ness in freestyle wrestling, highlighting the need for comprehensive support systems to address athletes' unique psychological needs effectively.

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative approach, synthesizing existing literature to elucidate the organizational and methodological requisites for effective psychological preparation in freestyle wrestling. Drawing upon theoretical frameworks and empirical evidence, it seeks to delineate practical strategies for optimizing athletes' psychological self-preparation.

Results and discussion.

The synthesis of literature underscores the imperative to integrate self-psychological-preparation-based approaches into psychological preparation strategies for freestyle wrestlers. By recognizing the independent preparation abilities of athletes, coaches and sports psychologists can tailor interventions to enhance individual performance. Key strategies include psychological self-assessment, personalized goal-

setting, self-regulation methods, cognitive-behavioral techniques, and stress management protocols. The findings underscore the need for a paradigm shift in the approach to psychological preparation in freestyle wrestling. While traditional methodologies have focused on generic techniques, there is a growing consensus on the importance of individualized interventions. By leveraging self-psychological-preparation-based approaches, coaches can optimize athletes' psychological readiness, thereby maximizing performance outcomes.

The Psychological Challenges in Pre-Competition Preparation: V.V. Frolov delineates three distinct periods during the pre-competition preparation stage, each with its set of tasks. However, athletes often find themselves grappling with psychological hurdles unique to each period. The uncertainty preceding the draw, the pressure of the impending races, and the intensity of competition demand a high level of mental resilience. Furthermore, the competitive experience, while invaluable, can also inflict significant emotional and physical tolls on athletes, underscoring the need for effective psychological preparation strategies.

Understanding the Sporting Character: E.M. Khoklov highlights the importance of certain characteristics in shaping a sporting character essential for success in competitive wrestling. These include calmness in extreme situations, self-confidence, and a fighting spirit. However, the cultivation of these traits requires deliberate effort and systematic training, which is often lacking in the current approach to psychological preparation.

Understanding the Challenges: Successful performance in competitions depends not only on physical, technical, and tactical preparedness but also on psychological readiness. Athletes must be psychologically prepared to tap into their full potential during competitions. However, the lack of structured psychological training leaves athletes to navigate these challenges independently, often without access to expert

guidance or tailored interventions. The absence of consideration for individual psychological characteristics further compounds the problem, hindering athletes' ability to perform at their best.

General vs. Specific Psychological Preparation: P.V. Trutnev distinguishes between general psychological preparation, which focuses on shaping ideological convictions and nurturing personality traits, and specific preparation tailored to the demands of individual competitions. While both forms of preparation are essential, athletes frequently lack access to specialized psychological training geared towards freestyle wrestling.

A Comprehensive Plan for Psychological Preparation: G.A. Kozlov emphasizes the necessity of a structured plan for psychological preparation, taking into account athletes' age, skill level, and individual characteristics. Such a plan should incorporate a range of activities aimed at developing mental resilience, emotional stability, and competitive mindset. However, the absence of standardized guidelines and resources often leaves athletes struggling to devise effective preparation strategies independently.

Pressure to Perform: One of the primary challenges faced by freestyle wrestlers is the pressure to perform consistently at a high level. As athletes aim to transition from good to elite status, the expectations placed upon them can induce anxiety and performance-related stress. Strategies such as stress management techniques, goal setting, and focusing on the process rather than outcomes can help athletes cope with this pressure. However, the lack of structured psychological training and guidance leaves athletes to navigate these strategies independently, often without access to expert support or tailored interventions.

Self-Confidence Issues: Fluctuations in self-confidence are common among wrestlers as they encounter more challenging opponents and higher expectations. Building and maintaining self-confidence

through positive self-talk, reinforcement of past successes, and seeking support from coaches and teammates are essential strategies. Nonetheless, the absence of systematic psychological self-preparation leaves athletes to grapple with self-confidence issues without comprehensive guidance or tailored interventions to address underlying factors contributing to their confidence fluctuations.

Fear of Failure: The fear of failure can be a significant barrier to skill improvement for freestyle wrestlers. Athletes may avoid taking risks or trying new techniques to prevent mistakes, thereby hindering their progress. Cultivating a growth mindset that views failures as opportunities for learning and growth is crucial. However, the lack of structured psychological self-regulation means that athletes must navigate this process independently, often without access to strategies or resources to help them overcome their fear of failure effectively.

Motivational Challenges: Maintaining motivation can be challenging, especially when progress seems slow or setbacks occur. Connecting goals to values and long-term aspirations can provide intrinsic motivation for athletes. However, the absence of systematic psychological self-preparation means that athletes may struggle to sustain motivation without structured guidance or interventions to help them navigate motivational challenges effectively and independently.

Managing Expectations: External pressures and expectations from coaches, parents, and peers can add to the complexity of elite-level competition for freestyle wrestlers. Balancing these expectations with personal goals and priorities requires effective communication and realistic goal setting. Nevertheless, the lack of structured psychological self-regulation means that athletes may face challenges in managing expectations independently, often without access to strategies or resources to help them navigate these complex dynamics effectively.

Psychological Fatigue: The demands of training, competition, and balancing other aspects of life can contribute to psychological fatigue for wrestlers. Implementing rest and recovery periods, prioritizing sleep and nutrition, and teaching stress management techniques are essential for mitigating psychological fatigue. However, the absence of systematic psychological self-regulation means that athletes may lack access to comprehensive support systems to help them manage psychological fatigue effectively.

Addressing the Gap: To bridge the gap in psychological self-preparation, a comprehensive approach is needed. This includes the development of structured psychological self-preparation programs tailored to independence of freestyle wrestlers. Coaches should work closely with sports psychologists to create individualized plans for athletes based on their age, skill level, and psychological characteristics. These plans should incorporate strategies for self-regulation, self-preparation, stress management, goal setting, self-confidence building, and emotional regulation.

Developing Comprehensive Support Systems: Psychological self-preparation should be integrated into the overall training regimen for freestyle wrestlers. This includes planning for pre-competition psychological self-preparation periods, where athletes undergo specific tasks independently to optimize their psychological readiness. Furthermore, competitions should be classified to help athletes prepare effectively for different types of events. General psychological preparation should be complemented with specific training tailored to individual competition requirements.

Conclusion.

The journey towards excellence in freestyle wrestling necessitates meticulous psychological preparation. While athletes demonstrate inherent resilience, the absence of structured psychological training and resources underscores a critical gap in their readiness. To bolster athletes' perfor-

mance and well-being, it is imperative to establish tailored support systems addressing the specific psychological needs of freestyle wrestlers. Through collaboration among coaches, sports psychologists, and support personnel, athletes can adeptly navigate the rigors of elite-level competition, transcending from proficient athletes to elite performers. The significance of effective psychological self-preparation cannot be overstated, particularly during the developmental stages of skill refinement. By recognizing and attending to athletes' independence, coaches and sports psychologists can optimize training methodologies and elevate performance outcomes on the mat. Psychological readiness stands as a linchpin for success and sustainability in competitive freestyle wrestling. Tackling obstacles such as inadequate training, dearth of guidance, and limited resources empowers athletes to cultivate optimal mental states and elevate their performance levels. The proposed model underscores the importance of customization, psychodiagnostics, and strategic planning, offering coaches a roadmap to orchestrate effective psychological self-preparation for freestyle wrestlers amidst skill enhancement phases. In essence, addressing the multifaceted challenges of psychological self-preparation during skill improvement stages mandates a holistic approach, encompassing structured training programs and accessible resources tailored to the distinct demands of competitive wrestling. Through concerted efforts in fostering psychological resilience and equipping athletes with requisite support, sports organizations can pave the way for enhanced performance prowess on the wrestling mat.

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